

Effect of polymer and temperature on the critical micellar concentration of aqueous sodium dodecyl sulfate

N. Surendra Babu and M. C. S. Subha*

Department of Chemistry, S. K. University, Anantapur-515 003, India

E-mail : mcsubha@rediffmail.com Fax : 91-08554-55244

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The critical micellar concentrations (cmc) of SDS in aqueous polyethylene glycol (M.W. 35000) solutions have been determined at different temperatures. The cmc of SDS increases with the increase in concentration of PEG and decreases with increase of temperature. The critical aggregation concentration (CAC) and polymer saturation point (PSP) decrease with increase in temperature. The effect of the increase in polymer concentration of CAC and PSP has been determined. The thermodynamic quantities associated with the PSP are computed. Intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ of the PEG increases with increase in SDS concentration.

Polymer-surfactant (PS) interaction which is similar to protein-surfactant interaction, has attracted much attention owing to their industrial applications^{1,2}. These studies indicate that polymers interact with surfactants by inducing micellization of surfactants on the polymer chain and after polymer gets saturated with the micelles, the excess surfactants form free micelles³. These polymer bound micelles have higher solubilizing power as well as viscosity in comparison to individual polymer or micelle. Here we report the effect of polymer concentration (PEG) in aqueous systems on cmc of SDS at different temperatures. The viscosity of the system is also determined at various temperatures to throw light on polymer-surfactant interaction.

Results and Discussion

The plots of specific conductance (k) versus surfactant concentration for the systems in various aqueous polymer solutions have been given in Fig. 1. These plots exhibit three linear regions, below the CAC, between the CAC and PSP, where micelle like aggregates develop, and above the PSP where co-existence of dynamic equilibrium of surfactant saturated polymer and regular micelles³ occurs. The CMC decreases with rise in temperature (8.79 mol dm⁻³ at 30° to 7.0 mol dm⁻³ at 45°) but not much variation is observed with change in polymer concentration. It is generally accepted that the polymer-surfactant binding starts at CAC². This binding is similar to micellization but occurs at a relatively lower concentration of surfactant. With the increase in surfactant concentration, a second transition known as CMC of the polymer-surfactant complex or the polymer-saturation point (PSP) is obtained⁴. Table 1 gives PSP values for PEG-SDS by conductance measurements. It

Fig. 1 Plots of specific conductance (K) vs [SDS] at different concentration of PEG at 30° (x) 0.00, (o) 0.001, (Δ) 0.0001% is seen that as temperature increases, the PSP values decrease, indicating the saturation of the polymer at lower concentration. This is because the micelles are present as a necklace² in the polymer chain where the neutral polymer molecule decreases the ion-ion repulsion. Increase in temperature does not have such effect on this necklace but the aggregation number of the surfactant decreases and hence PSP decreases. It is known that the CMC (PSP) in-

creases with increase in polymer concentration⁵ in solution. This is because as polymer concentration increases, more binding sites are available hence more surfactant is needed for micellization. That is PSP increases with increase in polymer concentration.

Table 1. Critical micellar concentration (cmc) and thermodynamic parameters of micellization for SDS in aqueous and aqueous PEG (35000 M.W.) solution at different temperatures

Polymer %	Temp. °C	cmc × 10 ³ mol dm ⁻³	-ΔG _m ^o kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔH _m ^o kJ mol ⁻¹	ΔS _m ^o J mol ⁻¹ K ⁻¹
0.000	30	8.79	39.72	19.86	196
	35	8.26	40.65	20.52	198
	40	7.60	41.71	21.19	200
	45	7.01	42.76	21.87	203
0.0001	30	10.4	38.95	8.78	157
	35	9.8	39.88	9.07	158
	40	9.5	40.66	9.37	159
	45	8.6	41.78	10.12	163
0.001	30	10.7	38.82	9.77	160
	35	10.1	39.73	10.10	161
	40	9.5	40.66	10.43	163
	45	8.9	41.62	10.77	164
0.002	30	11.3	38.58	8.02	153
	35	10.7	39.46	8.28	154
	40	10.1	40.38	8.56	156
	45	9.5	41.31	8.83	157
0.003	30	11.8	38.38	8.48	154
	35	11.2	39.26	8.76	155
	40	10.6	40.15	9.05	157
	45	10.0	41.07	9.34	158

Thermodynamic quantities : The standard free energy of micellization (ΔG_m^o) for the systems studied was calculated using the relation⁶,

$$\Delta G_m^o = (2 - p/n) RT \ln(\text{cmc}) \quad (1)$$

where *p* is the number of residual charges per micelle and *n* the micellar aggregation number. For ionic surfactants⁷ *p/n* = 0.2. CMC is taken in mole fraction scale. Further, stand-

Fig. 2. Plots of $\ln(\eta V/Nh)$ vs T^{-1} for 0.25% SDS + PEG system at different PEG concentrations : (o) 0.2, (Δ) 0.25, (□) 0.30, (●) 0.35, (x) 0.4%.

ard enthalpy of micellization (ΔH_m^o) and entropy of micellization (ΔS_m^o) were calculated using the relations⁸ (2) and (3),

$$\Delta H_m^o = [-RT^2 \delta \ln(\text{cmc})/\delta T] \quad (2)$$

$$\Delta S_m^o = (\Delta H_m^o - \Delta G_m^o)/T \quad (3)$$

To calculate ΔH_m^o, ln(cmc) is plotted against *T* and the slope of the straight line is taken as δ ln(cmc)/δ*T*. A linear plot is observed for aqueous polymer solutions. The data of ΔH_m^o, ΔS_m^o and ΔG_m^o are included in Table 2. The results show that ΔG_m^o values for the systems studied are negative and increase with increase in polymer concentration. An increase in temperature results in decrease of ΔG_m^o values. This is due to the decreased hydration of the hydrophilic surfactant head group at higher temperature. Addition of polymer to the aqueous solution of SDS results in the decrease of ΔS_m^o values due to the penetration of polymer into hydrophobic core of SDS thereby favouring micellization. ΔH_m^o values are positive, indicating the interactions to be endothermic. ΔS_m^o values are small and positive, and decrease with increase in polymer concentration. On plotting enthalpy vs entropy changes at various polymer concentrations, a linear correlation is obtained. This indicates that the polymer surfactant interaction in this condition depends only upon the entropy change. Such enthalpy-entropy compensation effect were observed earlier in many physicochemical processes^{8,9}.

Table 2. Standard free energy of transfer (-ΔG_{tr}^o) of surfactant micelle from pure aqueous solutions to aqueous polymer solution

Polymer %	Temp. °C	ΔG _{tr} ^o kJ mol ⁻¹
0.0001	30	0.763
	35	0.788
	40	0.895
	45	0.973
0.001	30	0.873
	35	0.927
	40	1.045
	45	1.136
0.002	30	1.139
	35	1.193
	40	1.332
	45	1.447
0.003	30	1.335
	35	1.404
	40	1.559
	45	1.691

Thermodynamic properties of transfer : Standard free energy values of transfer (ΔG_{tr}^o) of surfactant (SDS) from aqueous solution to PEG + water system were calculated using the relation¹⁰,

$$\Delta G_{tr}^{\circ} = (2 - p/n) RT \ln(\text{cmc}/\text{cmc}^*) \quad (4)$$

where cmc and cmc* represent the critical micelle concentration in water and polymer + water system, respectively. The ΔG_{tr}° values are presented in Table 2. The ΔG_{tr}° values for SDS system are negative, indicating the feasibility of transfer of SDS micelles from water to PEG + water system.

Viscosity studies : Viscosities of the polymer-surfactant solutions were determined using an Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer. Intrinsic viscosity of the polymer was determined in the presence of various amounts of SDS. It was observed that the intrinsic viscosity of the PEG increases with increase in the concentration of SDS in solution (Table 3). The intrinsic viscosity-temperature profile shows an increase in intrinsic viscosity with increase in temperature for all concentrations of SDS studied. This indicates that as temperature increases, solvent power increases and the solubility of polymer increases resulting in the uncoiling of the polymer chains, providing interaction possibility leading to an increase in $[\eta]$. A similar observation was made earlier¹¹ from the viscosity studies of polyacrylamide + water + surfactant system.

Table 3. Intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$, voluminosity (V_E) and shape factor (v) for the polyethylene glycol-SDS systems at different temperatures

[Surfactant] % (w/v)	Intrinsic viscosity $[\eta]$ (dl/g)				V_E^* dl g ⁻¹	v^*
	30°	35°	40°	45°		
0.10	0.32	0.38	0.40	0.59	0.147	2.61
0.25	0.40	0.52	0.60	1.16	0.199	2.61
0.50	0.50	0.78	1.18	1.26	0.297	2.62

*At 35°.

Various activation parameters for viscous flow were evaluated using Frenkel-Eyring equation¹²,

$$\ln(\eta v/Nh) = \Delta G_{vis}^{\ddagger}/RT = \Delta H_{vis}^{\ddagger}/RT - \Delta S_{vis}^{\ddagger}/R \quad (5)$$

where $\Delta H_{vis}^{\ddagger}$ and $\Delta S_{vis}^{\ddagger}$ are the enthalpy and entropy of activation for the viscous flow and V, N, h, R, T and $\Delta G_{vis}^{\ddagger}$ are molar volume of the solvent, Avagadro number, Planck constant, gas constant, temperature (K) and free energy of activation for the viscous flow respectively. $\ln(\eta v/Nh)$ plotted against T^{-1} yields a straight line (Fig. 2) with slope and intercept giving $\Delta H_{vis}^{\ddagger}$ and $\Delta S_{vis}^{\ddagger}$, respectively. On plotting $\Delta H_{vis}^{\ddagger}$ and $\Delta S_{vis}^{\ddagger}$ against polymer concentration and extrapolating to $C=0$, $\Delta H_{vis}^{\ddagger 0}$ and $\Delta S_{vis}^{\ddagger 0}$ values are obtained and hence $\Delta G_{vis}^{\ddagger 0}$ are computed at any given temperature. The values to be almost independent of surfactant concentration. These values are 62.3 ± 0.02 at 35° and 18.0 ± 0.9 kJ mol⁻¹ for $\Delta G_{vis}^{\ddagger 0}$ and $\Delta H_{vis}^{\ddagger 0}$, respectively, and of $\Delta G_{vis}^{\ddagger 0}$ is equal to -203.8 ± 1.2 kJ mol. This $\Delta H_{vis}^{\ddagger 0}$, is somewhat close to 17 kJ mol⁻¹, characteristic value of spherocolloids¹³.

The relative viscosity data at different concentrations

are used for the calculation of voluminosity (V_E) of polymer solutions, at a given temperature in presence of SDS. The V_E values were obtained^{12,14} by plotting Y against concentration C (g/dl), where

$$Y = (\eta_r^{0.5} - 1)/C(1.35 \eta_r^{0.5} - 0.1) \quad (6)$$

The straight-line thus obtained are extrapolated $C=0$ and intercept yielded V_E at 35° which are shown in Table 3. The shape factor (v)^{12,13} is then calculated from the equation,

$$[\eta] = v V_E \quad (7)$$

The shape factor gives us an idea about polymer molecules in solution. The values of shape factor (Table 3) are ~2.61, indicating the spherical conformation of macromolecules in the presence of the surfactant¹⁵. In computing the shape factor and viscosity it is assumed that the polymer surfactant systems is nothing but a polymer system where an additive surfactant is present. That is the effect of the presence of SDS on the polymer structure could be obtained.

Polyethylene glycol-SDS systems in aqueous solution are studied at various temperatures by conductance and viscosity. It is observed that SDS interacts with the polyethylene glycol, and the interaction is in general mildly exothermic. The system shows higher intrinsic viscosity indicating interaction. The shape of polyethylene glycol molecule in solution does not seem to change in the presence of surfactants. The PEG is somewhat surface active and also does not contain large hydrophilic group. However, the magnitude of thermodynamic quantities indicates mild interactions.

Experimental

Polyethylene glycol with an average molecular weight of 35000 and sodium dedecyl sulfate (SDS) (Aldrich) were used as such. Triple-distilled water with specific conductance of the order 10⁻⁶ S cm⁻¹ at 30° was used for preparing solutions. Specific conductance of the solutions was measured using an Elico conductometer. Concentration of the solution was varied by adding aliquots of concentrated stock solution to the known volume of the solution in the jacketed vessel with help of a micro syringe. Viscosity was measured using an Ubbelohde suspended level viscometer with an accuracy of $\pm 0.15\%$. All measurements were carried out in a constant temperature thermostat working at $\pm 0.005^\circ$.

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